

Review of Indoor, outdoor ^{222}Rn exposure assessment and modelling

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Abstract - In view of this, Indoor as well as outdoor radon concentration measurement has been carried out in specific residential and schools located in Mandya, Karnataka using well known SSNTD technique. The indoor radon level is predicted in the same selected dwellings using the suitable model which is based on the mass balance equation and the results are compared with the measured values. Annual mean values of ^{222}Rn in selected houses and schools were found to be 19.68 Bq m⁻³ respectively. Annual mean values in some other survey for ^{222}Rn and ^{220}Rn concentrations was found to be 22.4 and 24.1 Bq m⁻³ respectively. The total annual effective dose received by the general public due to radon and thoron is found to be 1.1 mSv y⁻¹, which is close to the Indian average value of 1.11 mSv y⁻¹. The doses to different organs and tissues were calculated using the ICRP model of the respiratory tract and inter comparison was discussed.

Keywords - ^{222}Rn ; SSNTD, Dosimetry, Indoor, Radon, Thoron, Effective dose, Modeling.

INTRODUCTION

In last couple of decades the ionizing radiations have got considerable attention because of their radiological hazards. Among all the natural sources of radiation dose to mankind, inhalation of radon (^{222}Rn), thoron (^{220}Rn) and their progeny contribute about 50% to global effective dose. It has recently become apparent that the behavior of ^{222}Rn , ^{220}Rn and their decay products in the atmosphere is important for the analysis of the transport of air pollutants and greenhouse gases which cause serious environmental problems [1, 2].

Ionizing radiation has enough energy to affect living tissues and thereby harm their genetic material (DNA). Fortunately, the cells in the body are efficiently repairing this limited damage by itself. However, if there is irreparable damage eventually a cell may die leads to cancer.

It has been shown that the risk coefficient for lung cancer is higher for children than that for adults. These radioactive mixtures gave health hazard not only to individuals working in Uranium mines, but also to public living in normal houses, working places like coal fields and other related industries. Many epidemiological and dosimetric studies have established a clear correlation between indoor radon and human health in recent decades [3, 4].

Measurements of radioactivity in air and terrestrial environment have been extensively studied Atmospheric

Radon concentration depends on the amount of ^{226}Ra in the underlying soils and/or rocks and their type, porosity, humidity, and temperature.

The radon concentration clearly varies from region to region. Moreover, Radon in atmosphere rapidly dissipates due to atmospheric dispersion which is strongly influenced by weather conditions such as precipitation and haze. Therefore, the outdoor Radon level depends on weather conditions. Some studies also reported that the radon concentration varied with seasons with the highest concentration generally in the winter months [5-9].

Annual effective dose to the Mandya population due to indoor radon exposure was estimated with the measurements of radon and thoron concentrations in two different phases.

The entry of ^{222}Rn and ^{220}Rn into the dwellings was shown in fig:1 and their concentrations was measured in houses for various parameters like age of the building, different flooring and roofing.

The outdoor radon level was also measured in the same dwelling with the same SSNTD technique. Using ICRP respiratory tract model doses due to ^{222}Rn to the different tissues and organs of the human body were calculated. Since the studies on indoor radon concentration in this area are limited, an attempt has been made to predict the indoor radon levels in various houses using an existing model and the results are compared with measured values.

Fig.2: Pictorial representation of entry of Radon into the dwelling

II. MATERIALS AND METHODS

The concentrations of ^{222}Rn and ^{220}Rn in the dwellings were calculated by the data from Solid State Nuclear Track Detectors (SSNTD). Solid State Nuclear Track Detectors are thin sheets of dielectric materials such as cellulose nitrate and polycarbonate.

For Indoor radon measurements, 12 μm thick LR115 type-II strippable cellulose nitrate films, supported on a transparent 100 μm thick polyester (cellulose acetate) sheet, made by Kodak Pathe, France were used which is shown in fig:2. The films are less influenced by the moderate humidity, heat and light.

The films were kept in the two compartments of single entry twin cup pinhole dosimeters. These plastic dosimeters were developed and calibrated at Environmental Assessment Division, Bhabha Atomic Research Centre, Mumbai.

The dosimeters are suspended overhead on the ceiling at a height of about 2.5 m from the floor and at least 10 cm away from any wall. The films were retrieved after 90 days, etched in an etching bath unit and tracks were counted using a spark counter. From the track density, radon and thoron gas concentrations were calculated [10].

Fig. 2 Twin cup pin hole dosimeter

Results and Discussions

Concentration of ^{222}Rn and ^{220}Rn in different residential dwellings(phase-1and in phase 2)

In phase 1 the ^{222}Rn and ^{220}Rn concentrations measured for a period of 1 year and their average values tabulated in Table 1. From the Table 1, it was observed that ^{222}Rn and ^{220}Rn concentration varies between 4.1 to 86.5 Bq m^{-3} , 5.2 to 81.5 Bq m^{-3} , respectively with a mean value of 22.4 Bq m^{-3} and 24.1 Bq m^{-3} respectively.

It has shown from the survey that about 89 % of the houses recorded radon levels is less than 40 Bq m^{-3} . The observed mean value of ^{222}Rn is well within the worldwide population averaged radon concentration of 40 Bq m^{-3} for indoors and the Indian average of 42 Bq m^{-3} [11, 12]. About 68% of the dwellings showed thoron concentration less than 20 Bq m^{-3} . Maximum ^{222}Rn and ^{220}Rn concentrations were observed in couple of places. The lower concentrations of ^{222}Rn and ^{220}Rn in majority of the dwellings just because the lower concentration of ^{226}Ra in the soil naturally and building materials will also to the good ventilation conditions in the local dwellings.

The inhalation dose (mSv y^{-1}) to the inhabitants due to the inhalation of ^{222}Rn and ^{220}Rn was estimated using the following relation [23].

$$\text{----- (1)}$$

Where FR and FT; the equilibrium factors for radon (0.4) and thoron (0.1) respectively corresponding to the extracted ventilation rate. The annual effective dose due to radon and Thoron was found to vary from 0.45 – 3.64 mSv y^{-1} with the mean value of 1.15 mSv y^{-1} slight higher than the Indian average value of 1.11 mSv y^{-1} [13-15].

Table-1: The average ^{222}Rn and ^{220}Rn concentration with different building parameters

	Type of Roofing and Flooring	Mean Concentration (Bq m^{-3})	Annual effective dose (mSv y^{-1})	
		^{222}Rn	^{220}Rn	
Roofing Type	Tile roofing	14.73	15.1	0.82
	RCC	31.61	27.3	1.62
	Asbestos	15.6	33.5	1.42
Flooring Type	Cement	14.21	23.94	1.06
	Tiles	17.6	14.7	0.89
	Granite	48.4	34.97	2.28
Overall	Red oxide	21.7	10.6	0.88
	Min-Max	04.1 to 86.5	5.2 to 81.5	0.48 to 3.97
	Mean	22.4	24..11	1.36

In phase -2 the different geological background was taken up and measurement of concentration of ^{222}Rn in indoor was carried out with SSNTD films were exposed for a period of 1 year (6 months duration, twice). The radon levels in the houses varied between 15.3 - 38.3 Bqm^{-3} with a mean value of 23.3 Bqm^{-3} . The mean ^{222}Rn concentrations in the schools were found to be of 17.4 Bqm^{-3} . The overall mean radon concentration is calculated as 20.3 Bqm^{-3} . The observed mean value is well within the worldwide, population-averaged ^{222}Rn concentration of 40 Bq m^{-3} for indoors and the Indian average of 42 Bq m^{-3} [16].

Variation of ^{222}Rn and ^{220}Rn concentrations with type of flooring, roofing and age of the buildings

The indoor ^{222}Rn and ^{220}Rn concentration measured in various types of floorings in the study area. The most common types of flooring materials used in the dwellings of Mandya are cement, tiles, granite and red-oxide. It may be seen from the table-1 that, the variation of ^{222}Rn and ^{220}Rn concentration follows the order Granite > Red-Oxide > Tiles > Cement and Granite > Cement > Tiles > Red-Oxide respectively as shown in fig-3.

Naturally the rocks of granite have abundant contents of ^{226}Ra , ^{232}Th and ^{40}K [17, 18]. The average value of ^{222}Rn and ^{220}Rn concentration was 48.5 and 34.97 Bq m^{-3} respectively reported in table 1. The peak value ^{222}Rn and ^{220}Rn concentration was found in building with Granite flooring.

Fig: Radon level for different flooring, roofing and age of the building

The houses with roofs; (i) Tiles (ii) RCC and (iii) asbestos were considered to study. Table 1 shows the Mean ^{222}Rn and ^{220}Rn concentration with different types of roofing. It was observed that, the variation of ^{222}Rn concentration follows the order RCC > Asbestos > Tiles. ^{222}Rn and ^{220}Rn concentration was more in RCC roofing compared to tiles and asbestos. It is observed that tiles and asbestos roofs give increased ventilation inside a room as compared with RCC roofing. The range and the frequency of ^{222}Rn and ^{220}Rn concentration were reported in table 2.

The information about approximate age of the dwellings was collected. Table 1 illustrates the mean of ^{222}Rn and ^{220}Rn concentration with age of the dwellings. In the present study, the selected residence with 120 years shows less ^{222}Rn and

220Rn concentration which has the typical design, bigger windows and also has wide space from neighboring buildings.

Table-2: Range and frequency of 222Rn with different roofing and flooring

	Trial no	Range of ²²² Rn concentration(Bq/m ³)	frequency
roofing	1	0-20	10
	2	20-40	02
	3	40-60	00
	4	60-80	00
	5	80-100	01
Flooring		0-20	10
		20-40	02
		40-60	00
		60-80	00
		80-100	01

Outdoor Radon concentration

The average concentrations during spring, summer, autumn and winter are 9.2, 6.1, 8.7 and 13.8 Bq m⁻³ respectively. The higher radon concentration in air during winter followed by the drop in the activity during summer and autumn / spring season may be attributed to the intense temperature inversion which occurs in winter, the vertical mixing and dispersion which occurs in summer, the rain washout during spring / autumn season and the decrease in the emanation of radon from soil when it is saturated with water during spring / autumn season

Js: Exhalation from soil; Jbm: Exhalation from building material; Sg: Surface area of flooring; Sbm: Surface area of building material; V: Volume of the room; λv: Ventilation rate; λ: Decay constant; Cs: Radon concentration in soil; Cbm: Radon concentration in building material.

Prediction of indoor 222Rn concentration by an existing Mathematical model. The final equation for estimating indoor radon concentrations deduced from the mass balance equation, solving the differential equation and by neglecting the decay constant, Eq (2) can be written as:

The actual and estimated 222Rn concentrations are in better agreement except for a few residential dwellings. fig. 3 shows the variation of measured and model predicted 222Rn concentration values in different residential dwellings of Mandya, Karnataka, India. The error is due to the equation used for the calculation of ventilation rate which is in fact the dominant parameter[19]

$$C_{in} = \frac{J_s \frac{S_g}{V} + J_{bm} \frac{S_{bm}}{V} + \lambda_v C_{out}}{\lambda + \lambda_v} \text{-----(2)}$$

Fig: Comparison of measured and predicted Rn concentration

III. CONCLUSIONS

The average value of the radon level is of 22.4 Bq m⁻³ well within world and the Indian average radon concentrations and of 42 Bq m⁻³. About 89 % of the dwellings showed radon concentration less than the Indian average concentration of 40 Bq m⁻³. The average effective inhalation doses are well within the action level proposed by ICRP 1993. The average outdoor radon concentration was observed to be 9.47Bq m⁻³. The peak value of 222Rn and 220Rn concentration was found in Granite flooring, RCC roofing among various different combinations. The solved differential equation taking in to account all the parameters written in the steady state predicts so exactly the indoor Rn concentration except for a few residences.

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